

Advances in Lightweight Precision North Finding and Positioning Systems

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Abstract

Far Target Location (FTL) is a key element of the US Army's Force Operating Capabilities (FOC) doctrine to see, understand, and act first and foremost on the battlefield. Precise FTL data provides today's Soldier with essential information pertaining to direct and indirect fire, surveillance, and maneuver missions, where reliable and accurate Situational Awareness (SA) is vitally important for dismounted military operations. The US Army in conjunction with our industry partners, have spent the last ten years canvassing the marketplace to develop, optimize, and make available for fielding a lightweight, low power and accurate north finder and position keeping inertial module. This effort has included the technologies of Fiber Optic Gyros (FOGs), Ring Laser Gyros (RLGs), Magnetohydrodynamic gyros (MHD), Hemispherical Resonator Gyros (HRG), and MicroElectroMechanical Systems gyros (MEMS) and various hybrid solutions. Included in these efforts have been major breakthroughs in the evolution of the technologies, many challenges, and a continuing effort to push the boundaries of what is possible in this rapidly changing field. This paper will cover the progress, present state, and visions for the future as it applies to the dismounted soldier and combat vehicle crew members.

1. Background

Precise Far Target Location (FTL) is a key element in order to see, understand, and act first and foremost on the battlefield. Precise FTL data provides today's Soldier with essential information pertaining to direct and indirect fire, surveillance, and maneuver missions, where reliable and accurate Situational Awareness (SA) is vitally important for dismounted military operations. The current fielded US Army man-portable target locators use a Digital Magnetic Compass (DMC) to determine target azimuth and vertical angle. Field reports and testing indicate the DMC's azimuth accuracy is highly susceptible to the magnetic effects of nearby objects, the earth's magnetic field variations, and improper calibration procedures. These causes of DMC error fluctuation are more critical when the need for precise accuracy is required. By improving FTL accuracy, the US Army looks to increase lethality, improve survivability, significantly reduce collateral damage, minimize non-combatant casualties, decrease the logistical burden of failed munitions, increase engagement ranges, and execute more precise maneuvers.

The US Army has investigated several inertial technologies that are not dependent on sensing Earth's magnetic field. From these investigations, Inertial based sensors were found to be the most robust and reliable for targeting application. Inertial sensors measure Earth's rotational rate and gravity vector to update a rigid body's attitude and position.

Inertial sensors primarily consist of gyroscopes and accelerometers, measuring the angular rates and linear accelerations respectively. To completely capture the motion of a rigid body, three orthogonal axis of linear and angular measurements are required. Thus, an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) consists of 3 or more gyroscopes and 3 or more accelerometers. The configuration utilized in all of the inertial configuration in this paper use 'strapdown' mode where the IMU is rigidly tied to the body in motion. An Inertial Navigation System (INS) is the system that consists of an IMU along with necessary algorithms to perform application specific function. Targeting application uses the gyrocompassing aspect of an INS. Gyrocompassing is a function of an INS where the measurements of Earth's rate from the gyroscopes and the gravity vector from the accelerometers are used to determine the body attitude angles (roll, pitch, and heading). Essentially, measurement from the accelerometers are used to determine the leveling angles for the INS while the gyros are utilized to measure the component of Earth's rate which is then used to determine the azimuth angle to true north.

2. Inertial Sensors and Error Parameters

There are several grades of INS - namely, strategic, navigation, tactical, automotive and consumer. Targeting is a very challenging application for the INS since, during the targeting, there is no motion of the body. Thus ancillary systems such as GPS cannot be used to initialize the heading and or estimate the error parameters of the inertial sensors. Thus, the requirements for the inertial sensors come very close to those of navigation grade INS.

Three gyro parameters that are of real importance for gyrocompassing are - turn-on to turn-on bias, bias instability, and Angle Random Walk (ARW). To gyrocompassing to 4 mils (1-sigma) in 90 seconds (at 60 degrees latitude), the combined bias errors have to be less than 0.03 degrees per hour (1-sigma) and an ARW of less than 0.005 degrees per sqrt(hr) (1-sigma). Additionally, the accelerometer bias shall be less than 2 mg (1-sigma) to achieve similar performance in roll and pitch angles. There are additional parameters such as scale factor errors, scale factory symmetry, g-sensitivity, magnetic field sensitivity, and temperature sensitivities that must be kept in mind.

Until recently, the only gyros that could support such performance were Ring Laser Gyros (RLG), Fiber Optic Gyro (FOG), and large Hemispherical Resonating Gyroscopes (HRG). With the investment from the US Army, there are two current inertial technologies that have the ability to provide the necessary accuracy with more desirable Size, Weight, and

Power (SWaP). These technology are Hemispherical Resonating Gyro (HRG) from SAGEM and Fiber Optic Gyro (FOG) from Emcore. Both technologies achieve the required azimuth accuracy and exploit phenomenon other than earth's magnetic field. These two approaches address the need for more accurate targeting information by determining the azimuth and vertical angle of the target by providing an azimuth accuracy of < 4 mils (at 60 degrees latitude and over Military operational conditions) and a vertical angle accuracy of < 2 mils.

3. Current Capabilities

SAGEM has developed a three axis INS that incorporates three Hemispherical Resonating Gyros (HRG)s and three MEMS based accelerometers. HRGs, also known as wine glass resonators, work on the principle of forming a standing wave on the rim of the structure. As the structure (shown in Figure 1) rotates, the wave trails the rotation at a mathematically predictable rate. This rate can be measured and used as a basis for determining the rotation of the structure.

Figure 1 HRG resonator

Modern day HRGs can do this with astounding precision and low noise yielding sensors capable of detecting the rotation of the earth around its axis. This is used to determine the orientation of the axis of rotation, which yields true north. The current HRG INS design (shown in Figure 2) utilizes the HRGs to determine angular changes with three orthogonal accelerometers to measure linear accelerations. Both North Finding and North Keeping modes have been incorporated in mature algorithms intended to operate through the various testing conditions expected. Future upgrades may allow position keeping through GPS challenged environments as well.

Figure 2 Three axis HRG INS

As mentioned above, Emcore has developed a FOG based approach tailored to Soldier Targeting Applications. In order to reduce the SWaP, there is one large North Finding Gyro and then two smaller nested gyros that when coupled with the larger winding provide the North Keeping capability, as shown in Figure 3. FOGs have long been used for Navigation grade applications, but this is one of the first implementations of the technology in a truly man portable package.

Figure 3 FOG based approach

4. Next Generation Inertial Sensors

To reach the desirable SWaP and performance, revolutionary Micro-Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS) technology is being pursued. Until recently, MEMS gyroscope

performance was limited to tactical, automotive or consumer grade performance. Recent developments, primarily funded by US Army Night Vision and Electronic Sensors Directorate (NVESD) and DARPA has helped in the development of MEMS in-situ calibration features for MEMS that does not require any mechanical mechanism. Some of these features have been demonstrated to achieve navigation grade performance under limited environmental conditions. Current MEMS technology being investigated for north-finding / north-keeping contain all the desirable attributes except the necessary navigation grade performance for precision FTL. MEMS gyroscopes suffer from turn-on to turn-on bias variability and electronic noise. The MEMS gyro industry has addressed both of these concerns adequately. Employment of efficient Analog to Digital converters and low noise electronics have addressed a significant aspect of the noise on the angular rate measurements. It is well known that symmetry within a gyroscope resonating structure can be exploited to perform in-situ calibration techniques. In addition, accurate and efficient micro fabrication techniques along with error nulling techniques, have enabled the MEMS to achieve navigation grade performance.

There are two US government funded MEMS efforts that have now demonstrated navigation grade performance under limited environmental conditions. These are efforts on Disk Resonating Gyroscopes (DRG) by Sensors in Motion (SIM) and Boeing. DRG is a specific MEMS gyroscope that utilizes Coriolis force for estimating body rotation. DRG resonator are 4 - 8 mm in diameter with 100 - 300 um wall thickness (shown in figure 4 below). DRG uses capacitive drive and pickoff with two degenerate modes similar to HRG. Current Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) estimates on the IMU based on DRG is <8 cubic inches, <1 lb, and <5 W.

Figure 4 Disk Resonating Gyroscope (DRG) structure

Figure 5 SIM DRG based INS

There is one other effort that is funded by the US government that uses MEMS sensors on a mechanical rotary stage to cancel the inherent biases in the gyro measurements. The proposed system by Honeywell with this configuration has very desirable SWaP characteristics <8 cubic inches, <1 lb, and <5 W. Figure 6 shows an intermediate milestone hardware that has potential for further SWaP reduction.

Figure 6 Honeywell MEMS INS

5. Adjunct Sensor (Celestial Compass)

One of the adjunct sensor developed by the US Army Program Manager - Soldier Precision Targeting Devices (PM-SPTD) is a Celestial Compass (CC). A CC uses the image of the sun and stars along with solar ephemeris and the star catalogue to determine the true azimuth. A CC also uses inclinometers to determine the roll and the pitch angles.

A CC has one day camera and one or more night camera that gathers images of the Sun and starts in the visible part of the sky. CC can determine the true azimuth in less than 10 seconds (day or night) when the celestial objects are clearly visible. CC have a high Technological Readiness Level (TRL) > 7. The only weakness of this approach is lack of availability when the visible part of the sky is obstructed. An artistic rendition of a two camera CC is shown in figure 7 below. The SWaP for CC are <4 cubic inches, <.25 lb, and <1.5 W. The azimuth and tilt accuracies of the CC is shown to be < 2 mils (1-sigma).

Figure 7 A two camera celestial compass

Efforts are ongoing to amend the CC with detecting sky polarization capability - which then can provide degraded performance when the CC is unavailable due to obstruction of the sky to the CC cameras.

6. Operational Scenario

For the purposes of testing the performance of the north finder systems and the celestial compass, an extensive project of data collection was commissioned and executed by the UA army. The intent was to study the soldiers' motion profile as they conducted realistic missions. Data was also collected on the soldier's legs, chest and backpack with various maneuvers such as walk, run, crawl etc. The data was amended with hand jitter and tripod jitter (in the wind and on a deck with soldiers walking). A data collection system was designed to collect three dimensional linear accelerations and three dimensional angular rates in a box that is comparable in weight and size of a target location system. Figure 8 shows the designed Inertial Data Recorder (IDR) that used Honeywell HG 1930 IMU.

Figure 8 Inertial Data Recorder

Figure 9 shows one example of data collected using IDR during this exercise.

Figure 9 IDR Data Collection

For the purposes of bounding the user motion, it was found that maximum angular rate that an IMU is subjected to about 800 degrees per second and the maximum acceleration was about 10 g.

7. Summary and Conclusions

Azimuth determination is important in variety of military application from targeting to Augmented Reality to operations in GPS challenged operations. Navigation grade performance (from gyros and accelerometers) is required to meet the targeting objectives.

Over the past ten years, the US Army has made dramatic improvements in the performance of sensors in this Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) class. This has allowed for the first ever precision targeting man portable targeting system to become a reality. This capability is currently fulfilled by an optimized version of HRG and FOG. But these technologies are closing in on their minimal physical size and power limits.

To fully meet our objectives, the US Army is continually investing into MEMS based inertial sensors. Several MEMS solutions, such as DRGs, are currently being pursued that have achieved navigation grade performance in limited environmental conditions. Continual development of navigation grade accelerometer in a MEMS package is essential in achieving the truly man portable INS objective for targeting and position keeping capability.

Adjunct sensors, such as celestial and sky polarization compass, vastly expands our current capabilities, but have limitations that only inertial solutions can overcome. The celestial compass has very desirable SWaP attributes but suffers from the limited availability due to direct visibility to the celestial bodies.